

Table S1 Primers designed for qRT-PCR

Gene Name	Sequences 5'→3'
human-NMNAT1 F	TCATCATGGCAGAACTTGCT
human-NMNAT1 R	TGGCACAGCTTTTGTTTTGT
human-NMNAT2 F	GGCACCGTCTCATCATGTGTCAG
human-NMNAT2 R	CCCAAGATCTTGGCTGCAGTG
human-NMNAT3 F	CCCTGCAAATAGCAGCTACC
human-NMNAT3 R	TGAGAAGCTGCGAGGTCTTT
human-NAMPT F	ATCCTGTTCCAGGCTATTCTGT
human-NAMPT R	CCCATATTTTCTCACACGCAT
human-NMRK2 F	AGGATGACTTCTTCAAGCCCC
human-NMRK2 R	GGGCACGGGCAAACCTTCT
human-SIRT1 F	ACAGGTTGCGGGAATCCAAAGG
human-SIRT1 R	CCTAGGACATCGAGGAACTACCTG
human-SIRT2 F	ACCCGCTAAGCTGGATGAAAGAG
human-SIRT2 R	AGTCTTCACACTTGGGCGTCAC
human-SIRT3 F	ACATCGATGGGCTTGAGAGAGTG
human-SIRT3 R	CAGAGGCAAAGGTTCCATGAGC
human-SIRT4 F	ACAGGGTCCCTGTGCTTGGATTG
human-SIRT4 R	CTTGAAACGCTCTTGCAGCAC
human-SIRT5 F	TGGCTCGGCCAAGTTCAAGTATG
human-SIRT5 R	AAGGTCGGAACACCACTTTCTGC
human-SIRT6 F	TGTGGAAGAATGTGCCAAGT
human-SIRT6 R	CTTAGCCACGGTGCAGAG
human-SIRT7 F	GCGTCTATCCCAGACTACCG
human-SIRT7 R	GTGATGCTCATGTGGGTGA
human-CD38 F	GCTCAATGGATCCCGCAGTA
human-CD38 R	GGATCCTGGCATAAGTCTCTGG
human-PARP1 F	GCAACCACACACAATGCGTA
human-PARP1 R	GTTGGCACTCTTGGAGACCA
human-PARP2 F	GCATGACTTTGGACTCCGTA
human-PARP2 R	GCAATTTCAATGTCTCCCAA
human-PARP3 F	CCTCTGTCCACCTTCACCAC
human-PARP3 R	CATCCAGCTGCTCCAAGACA
human-PARP4 F	TTGACAAGTCACTCTAAGCTG
human-PARP4 R	AGGAGCAAAAACTAAGGCCT
human-PARP6 F	AGTTCTGGAATGATGACGACTCG
human-PARP6 R	GTGGGTGTGCGATACAGGTCAG
human-PARP9 F	ACAGGAGGAAATGGCAAGGAA
human-PARP9 R	TTGGAGGCACAGGACATTTCAG
human-PARP10 F	ATGGTT GCAATGGCGGAGGCAGA
human-PARP10 R	TCCAGGTACAA CTCCAGCAACA

human-PARP12 F	GTACAGAACCTGGCCCTCTG
human-PARP12 R	GACCCGCCAGTCAAAGTTCT
human-PARP14 F	G TTCAGCGCCTCACGAAATC
human-PARP14 R	TGGCCATTCTTGGCATCCAT
human-GAPDH-F	CCAGGTGGTCTCCTCTGA
human-GAPDH-R	GCTGTAGCCAAATCGTTGT
human-EV-D68-VP1-F (Fermon)	GTGGTCCCTAGTCTAAATGCAG
human-EV-D68-VP1-R (Fermon)	TAACGTCTCCGACACACCATG
human-EV-D68-VP1-F (ATCC VR-1824)	GTGGTCCCTAGTCTAAATGCAG
human-EV-D68-VP1-R (ATCC VR-1824)	CAAGGTCTCGGATACACCGTG
Mouse-GAPDH-F	AGGTCGGTGTGAACGGATTG
Mouse-GAPDH-R	GGGGTCGTTGATGGCAACA

Table S2 Primers designed for siRNA

Gene Name	Sequences 5'→3'
human-si SIRT1#1	GACUCAAGUUCACCAGAAATT
human-si SIRT1#2	UUCAAUAUCAACAUCGCUTT
human-si SIRT1#3	UUUCUGGUGAACUUGAGUCTT

Table S3 Primers designed for PCR

Gene Name	Sequences 5'→3'
Sirt1mt1-R	aaaGCTCTTCa <u>CCG</u> CGGCCTCTTGCGGAGCGGCT
Sirt1mt1-F	aaaGCTCTTCa <u>CGG</u> GAGAGATGGTCCCGGCCTCGAG
Sirt1mt2-F	cccGCTCTTCg <u>AAAA</u> AAAAGAAAAGATATTAATACAATTGAAGATGC
Sirt1mt2-R	cccGCTCTTCg <u>TTT</u> CCTTTTGGTGGTTCTGAAAGG
SIRT1-F	aaa <u>GTCGAC</u> CGCCACCATGGCGGACGAGGCGGCCCT
SIRT1-R	ggg <u>TCTAGAT</u> GATTTGTTTGATGGATAGTTCATGTCTG